

Developing an Android Application '*Haba Inggreh*' for Interactive Learning on Speaking and Listening Skills

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ABSTRACT

Published Online: August 24, 2024

The aim of this research is to design teaching materials for the listening and speaking learning process on the basis of independent learning with a focus on students through the technology-based android application '*Haba Inggreh*'. The Android application "*Haba Inggreh*" can be the right solution to solve listening and speaking problems because students can directly access the material and sentences they want and there is a feature to view scores. The research design used was Research and Development design involving six steps: need analysis, app development, app trial 1, app revision, and app trial 2. There were 6 high schools in Nagan Raya involved in this study as the respondents. The data collection was done following the R&D steps. After that, the data were analyzed using interactive analysis. The results show that, first, the students already have high motivation and good knowledge on technology-integrated learning; second, they have positive perception on the use of *Haba Inggreh* learning application. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of mobile learning in the ELT process can enhance the students' motivation and well as knowledge in language learning process.

KEYWORDS:

interactive teaching material; android app; online learning; education digitization; English learning.

INTRODUCTION

This research is important to carry out because nowadays, technology and education increasingly have to go hand in hand. The emergence of globalization has made information and communication technology something different in its application today (Sutarman et al., 2015; Haji, 2022). Increasing technological efficiency in various fields, especially those related to time, energy and costs, is facilitated by the dissemination of fast and accurate information (Gallagher, et al., 2024; Mayer, 2001). Basically, this research is a continuation of the results of

Corresponding Author: Veni Nella Syahputri

**Cite this Article: Veni Nella Syahputri, Nyak Mutia Ismail, Kismullah, Herri Darsan (2024). Developing an Android Application '*Haba Inggreh*' for Interactive Learning on Speaking and Listening Skills. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(8), 919-928*

previous research that had been carried out by the researchers entitled Reinforcing Teacher's Instructional Capability: Web-Designing. In this quantitative research, 15 teachers in Nagan Raya were involved as samples during the pandemic. At that time, teachers had to master adequate skills in implementing technology-based learning. And the results also improved after giving treatment. After the pandemic, technology-based learning methods and models continued with the splendor of the industrial era 4.0. So, from this factual situation, the researchers consider that students in Nagan Raya must also be able to carry out technology-based learning both guided and independently. This situation encourages app developers to engage in a competitive environment to design functional and mobile-centric apps. Therefore, Android smartphones, as one of the mobile devices used by all groups today, can be an alternative means of gaining knowledge about various English language skills (Aini & Riyantomo, 2019). The availability of English learning applications can serve as a

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valuable tool for any student who wishes to gain proficiency in English, especially for students who wish to achieve fluency in a timely manner (Binato, 2008). Therefore, researchers are encouraged to develop the best Android application that will help students learn English in speaking and listening in an integrated and interactive manner.

Interactivity is an important component of effective learning (Pramoto, 2006), because it actively involves learners in the learning process and provides opportunities for them to apply and practice what they have learned. When learners are actively involved in the learning process, they are more likely to retain information and be able to apply it in real-world situations [Harmer, 2007]. In this post-pandemic era, the effectiveness offered by online learning can no longer be marginalized. However, on the other hand, online learning is asynchronous, making learning less interactive, and it even gives the impression that the teacher is not involved, only giving assignments [Garrison, 1993]. This is the problem raised in this research.

Several previous studies have examined the use of Android applications to improve speaking and listening skills in English. However, none of these studies have designed a basic application for learning English related to speaking and listening skills so that it can be used by students in everyday learning. So, the novelty of this research is developing an Android application called *Haba Inggreh* to improve students' speaking and listening skills in the Nagan Raya area. It is hoped that the development of this application can be a solution in overcoming the problem of students' low ability in English, especially in speaking and listening skills. Apart from that, the results of this research were carried out further research in the form of community service on an international scale, namely in an immigration village in Thailand. It is hoped that the success that has been achieved would have a widespread impact.

The Android application that was designed included quizzes and assessments to test students' knowledge on speaking and listening. This can help students understand their strengths and weaknesses and adjust their learning strategies accordingly [Plass, et al., 2010; Suyono, 2016]. This application also includes simulations and visualizations that allow students to interact with complex concepts and ideas. This can help students understand abstract concepts by providing them with concrete representations.

Apart from that, the Android application which is named '*Haba Inggreh*' is designed to encourage collaboration, especially in the form of peer review. What is considered more significant is that the application is designed to provide a personalized learning experience based on the learner's interests, learning style and progress. This can help students stay motivated and involved in the learning process independently [Stoten, 2012; Artino, 2009].

Developing Android applications for learning to speak and listen in English can offer several new things compared to

traditional language learning methods, including accessibility, interactivity, personalization, gamification, and multimodal learning (Bates, et al., 2004). This can help students stay motivated and involved in the learning process. In addition, there is gamification of learning which makes learning more interesting and motivating. And of course, android apps can combine multiple learning modes, including audio, video, and text, to meet different learning styles and preferences (Lutfiansyah, 2016).

In 2021 the research team has designed a web-design as a distance interactive learning medium for teachers in Nagan Raya Regency. This web-design with the name *Cakrawala Guru* contains online learning features and in general there are English learning materials according to educational level. The results of implementing web-design in the English language learning process are very significant, this is proven by the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores obtained by teachers as research targets. However, the web design that has been designed does not yet provide special learning features for speaking and listening. Artino (2009) emphasized that learning listening needs to be trained with speaking skills so that you get maximum results. This is because what is heard will be said automatically, so repeated practice will improve speaking skills.

The application that was designed in the research is an innovative offer in learning for the Nagan Raya district area. This can be said because this agricultural area is not yet familiar with the application of technology and digitalization. So, the Android application "*Haba Inggreh*" can be the right solution to solve this problem. This is in line with the Ministry of Education and Culture's mission in implementing the Indonesian President's direction, namely: creating secondary education that is relevant and of high quality, equitable and sustainable, supported by infrastructure and technology. Hence, the research questions being formulated is as shown below:

1. *To what extent is the students' motivation and technology familiarity regarding technology-learning integration?*
2. *What is the students' perception after using Haba Inggreh application?*

LITERATURE REVIEW

Android application in Language Learning

In today's globalized world, the ability to communicate in multiple languages has become increasingly important. Language learning is not only a gateway to understanding different cultures but also an essential skill for professional and personal growth. One of the most effective and convenient tools for language learning today is the Android app. These applications offer a variety of features that cater to different learning styles and needs, making language acquisition accessible to anyone with a smartphone. This essay explores the various aspects of Android apps designed

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for language learning, highlighting their features, benefits, and impact on learners. Android language learning apps are designed to be user-friendly and interactive, making the learning process engaging and enjoyable. These apps often include a range of multimedia elements such as audio, video, and text, which cater to different learning preferences. For instance, apps like Duolingo and Babbel use gamification techniques to make learning fun and interactive. Users earn points, unlock new levels, and receive rewards for completing lessons, which motivates them to continue learning. This gamified approach not only keeps learners engaged but also helps reinforce the material through repeated practice (Kang, 2024).

One of the significant advantages of using Android apps for language learning is the flexibility they offer. Unlike traditional classroom settings, learners can access these apps anytime and anywhere, making it easier to fit language study into their busy schedules. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for working professionals, students, and travelers who may not have the time to attend regular classes. Additionally, many language learning apps offer offline mode, allowing users to download lessons and study without an internet connection. This feature ensures that learners can continue their language practice even in areas with limited connectivity. Another key benefit of Android language learning apps is their ability to provide personalized learning experiences (Lotan & Patil, 2023). These apps often use algorithms to track users' progress and adapt the content to their individual needs. For example, apps like Memrise and Rosetta Stone use spaced repetition techniques to help learners retain vocabulary and grammar rules more effectively. By analyzing users' performance, these apps can identify areas where they struggle and provide targeted exercises to address those weaknesses. This personalized approach ensures that learners receive the appropriate level of challenge and support, which can significantly enhance their language acquisition.

Android language learning apps also foster a sense of community among learners. Many apps include social features that allow users to connect with other language learners from around the world. This mutual exchange not only provides learners with the opportunity to practice speaking and listening skills but also exposes them to different cultures and perspectives. Additionally, many apps have forums, chat groups, and discussion boards where users can ask questions, share tips, and encourage each other. This sense of community can be incredibly motivating and can help learners stay committed to their language goals (Siregar, 2020).

The integration of advanced technologies in Android language learning apps has also revolutionized the way people learn languages. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are increasingly being used to enhance the learning experience. For example, AI-powered chatbots in

apps like Mondly and Replika simulate real-life conversations, allowing learners to practice speaking in a safe and controlled environment (Kruchinin & Bagrova, 2021). These chatbots can provide instant feedback on pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary usage, helping learners improve their language skills more effectively. Additionally, speech recognition technology enables apps to evaluate users' pronunciation and provide corrective feedback, which is crucial for developing accurate speaking skills.

Moreover, Android language learning apps often incorporate cultural content to provide learners with a deeper understanding of the language they are studying. For instance, some apps include cultural notes, idiomatic expressions, and real-life scenarios to help users grasp the context in which certain phrases are used. This cultural immersion is essential for developing not only linguistic competence but also cultural competence. By learning about the customs, traditions, and social norms of the target language's speakers, learners can communicate more effectively and respectfully in real-world situations (Mohammadi et al., 2020).

Interactive learning through android learning app

Interactive learning has emerged as a cornerstone of modern education, fundamentally transforming the way students engage with educational content. Unlike traditional passive learning, where students are mere recipients of information, interactive learning involves active participation, encouraging students to engage, explore, and collaborate. This dynamic approach enhances understanding, retention, and application of knowledge, making learning a more effective and enjoyable process. Android learning apps have capitalized on these principles, offering learners a myriad of interactive features that make education accessible, personalized, and engaging (Karnekar et al., 2024).

One of the key aspects of interactive learning is its ability to create an engaging educational environment. By involving students in the learning process, it transforms passive reception into active involvement. This is achieved through various methods such as quizzes, interactive simulations, and real-time feedback. For example, Android apps like Kahoot! and Quizlet use gamification to make learning fun and competitive. These apps allow students to participate in live quizzes, compete with peers, and receive instant feedback, which not only reinforces learning but also maintains high levels of student motivation and interest (Oliveira et al., 2021). Moreover, interactive learning promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Instead of simply memorizing facts, students are encouraged to analyze information, make connections, and apply their knowledge to real-world scenarios. Android apps also exemplify this by helping students understand complex concepts through guided problem-solving and step-by-step

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explanations. These apps enable learners to ask questions, explore different solutions, and understand the underlying principles behind each problem, fostering a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter.

Collaboration is another crucial element of interactive learning. It encourages students to work together, share ideas, and learn from each other's perspectives. Android apps like Google Classroom and Padlet facilitate collaborative learning by providing platforms where students can collaborate on projects, share resources, and provide peer feedback. Such collaboration not only enhances learning outcomes but also helps develop essential social and communication skills, preparing students for future collaborative work environments. Personalization is a significant advantage offered by interactive learning through Android apps. These apps often use algorithms to track student progress and tailor the learning experience to individual needs. For instance, apps like Duolingo and Khan Academy adapt their content based on the user's performance, ensuring that learners receive the right level of challenge. This personalized approach helps address each learner's unique strengths and weaknesses, making education more effective and efficient (Hidayati & Endayani, 2019). Furthermore, Android learning apps provide a flexible and convenient platform for interactive learning. Students can access educational content anytime and anywhere, making it easier to fit learning into their daily routines. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for those with busy schedules or varying learning paces. The ability to learn on-the-go and at one's own pace makes education more accessible to a broader audience, breaking down geographical and time barriers.

Speaking and listening skills in Technology 4.0 era

The advent of the Technology 4.0 era has revolutionized many aspects of our daily lives, including how we learn and communicate. This era, characterized by advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT), and augmented reality (AR), has significantly impacted education, particularly in the realms of speaking and listening skills. These technological advancements provide new opportunities and methodologies for improving communication abilities, making language learning more efficient, interactive, and accessible.

In the Technology 4.0 era, learning to speak and listen effectively is increasingly facilitated by AI-driven language learning platforms (Yousem, 2008). These platforms offer personalized learning experiences that adapt to the user's progress and learning style. AI algorithms analyze users' performance in real-time, providing instant feedback and adjusting the difficulty of exercises accordingly. This personalization ensures that learners receive the right level

of challenge and support, which is crucial for developing speaking and listening skills.

One of the most significant contributions of Technology 4.0 to language learning is the use of speech recognition technology (Junining, et al., 2020). Apps and platforms now incorporate advanced speech recognition systems that can accurately evaluate a learner's pronunciation and fluency. For instance, apps like Elsa Speak and Mondly use AI to provide instant feedback on pronunciation, helping learners improve their speaking skills through targeted practice. This technology not only helps learners develop correct pronunciation but also boosts their confidence in speaking a new language. Virtual and augmented reality technologies are also playing a crucial role in enhancing speaking and listening skills. VR and AR provide immersive environments where learners can practice real-life conversations in a controlled and safe setting. For example, platforms like Mondly VR allow users to engage in simulated conversations with virtual characters, providing a realistic context for practicing speaking and listening. These immersive experiences help learners become more comfortable with real-world communication, bridging the gap between classroom learning and actual language use.

Another notable development in Technology 4.0 is the use of machine learning algorithms to enhance listening comprehension. Platforms like Audible and Spotify offer language learning podcasts and audiobooks that use AI to recommend content based on the learner's proficiency level and interests. These resources provide authentic listening practice, exposing learners to different accents, dialects, and speaking styles, which are essential for developing comprehensive listening skills. The Technology 4.0 era also promotes collaborative learning through online communities and interactive platforms (Karim et al., 2018). Learners can participate in virtual language classes, join discussion forums, and engage in group projects, all of which enhance speaking and listening skills through peer interaction and feedback. Platforms like Zoom and Microsoft Teams have made it possible to attend live language classes and workshops from anywhere in the world, providing opportunities for real-time practice and interaction (Bağcı & Pekşen, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

This research uses R&D research methods. R&D is an abbreviation for Research and Development, which is the process of investigating, developing, and testing new ideas, products, services, and processes. The aim of R&D research is to create new knowledge and innovation that can lead to the development of new products or services, or improvements to existing ones [Creswell, 2013; Sugiyono, 2013]. There are 5 stages that were implemented using the R&D method in this research. The first stage was needs analysis, where it was found that students' needs for

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technology-based learning processes in Nagan Raya were increasing. The second stage is the initiation of product ideas/planning. In this research, the Android application 'Haba Inggreh' was produced to overcome existing problems and take advantage of new opportunities in digitizing learning. The third stage is the initial research or trial phase, where researchers conducted in-depth research to collect information and analyze data related to the android application idea 'Haba Inggreh'. The fourth stage is product revision. Based on implementation, the concept is tested and refined. This involves creating a detailed plan and outlining the specifications, features, and functionality of this application with the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI). This may involve several learning methods experts. After this stage there was a prototype of the *Haba Inggreh* application. After that, the final stage is initial testing. This step helps refine this application and ensure it meets the required specifications and standards.

Regarding the respondents, the following is data from the schools that were involved as the research population. There were 6 high schools involved, they are SMAN 1 Darul Makmur with 394 students, SMAN 1 Seunagan with 637 students, SMAN 1 Kuala with 351 students, SMAN 1 Tadu Raya with 48 students, SMAN 1 Suka Makmue with 22 students, and SMAN 1 Beutong with 323 students. The students agreed to be involved as the respondents in this study and they were all willing to honestly give comments and testimony on the implementation of the app trial stage. The respondents were taken by using purposive sampling with one criterion—they be a student in one of Nagan Raya high schools regardless of the grade.

In concern to the data collection process, after finding the main problems in general and specifically in teaching speaking and listening in schools in the above sub-districts, the head and members of the research team started collecting data using the Online Technologies Self-Efficacy Scale (OTSES) questionnaire and the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire test. (MSLQ) adapted from Wang et al [Wang, et al., 2013]. After the initial data is obtained, prototype development was carried out. After the initial prototype is complete, it was made to the first trial to students at SMAN 1 Darul Makmur and SMAN 1 Seunagan. Next, the students were given the questionnaires and the data from this questionnaire is considered as the revision data. The data were merely descriptive and it was analyzed using three-step analysis. After the improvement stage, this application was tested for use with the rest of the high schools in Nagan Raya district. Then an expert analysis will be carried out on the shortcomings of the 'Haba English' application. The instruments that will be used this year are checklists and interviews to examine in depth the shortcomings. Followed by data analysis and interpretation using three-step analysis (data reduction, data display, and data verification) as suggested by Miles, et al (2014).

In addition, the students' perception on the use of the application was measured. The instrument used at this stage is a questionnaire which is classified into 4 parts, namely in terms of interactivity, interest and motivation, structured independent learning, and practicality (Raut, et al., 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In attempt to answer the first research question, research questionnaire was conducted across six high schools reveals detailed insights into students' motivation, familiarity with technology, and their perception of the *Haba Inggreh* application.

In SMAN 1 Beutong, 30 students participated in the survey, revealing that 90% of them are highly motivated to succeed in learning English. This strong motivation suggests a generally positive attitude towards English education and a recognition of its importance. However, there is a significant gap in technological familiarity, as only 40% of the students are aware of Zoom, indicating limited exposure to online learning platforms. This lack of familiarity with Zoom may reflect broader issues such as limited access to resources or insufficient emphasis on digital literacy in their curriculum.

Despite this gap, most students are proficient in browsing Google, which shows they possess basic digital skills necessary for research and information gathering. Additionally, 90% of the students have social media accounts, indicating that they are engaged in digital communication and social networking, which can be enhanced for educational purposes.

At SMAN 1 Seunagan, the survey included 38 students, with an impressive 97% expressing a strong desire to succeed in learning English. This high level of motivation suggests a robust recognition of the importance of English proficiency for their academic and professional futures.

Technological familiarity among these students is notably high. A significant 90% of students are familiar with Zoom, indicating that they have access to and are likely using advanced digital learning tools. This familiarity suggests that the students are better equipped to adapt to various online learning environments, an essential skill in today's increasingly digital world. Additionally, the fact that 100% of students can browse Google reflects a solid foundation in digital literacy, enabling them to efficiently access and use online resources for their studies. The universal presence of social media accounts further emphasizes their digital engagement and comfort with technology.

SMAN 1 Suka Makmue had 28 students participating in the survey, with an impressive 95% of these students motivated to succeed in learning English. This high level of motivation indicates a strong appreciation for the importance of English language skills, likely driven by the recognition of its value in academic and future career prospects.

In terms of technological familiarity, 70% of the students are aware of Zoom, suggesting that a majority have some

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exposure to online learning platforms. However, the 30% who are not familiar with Zoom indicate a gap that could be due to limited access to such technologies or a lack of emphasis on their use within the school's curriculum. This gap in familiarity could potentially hinder these students' ability to fully engage in modern digital learning environments.

In SMAN 1 Kuala, 37 students were surveyed, and the results closely mirror those of SMAN 1 Seunagan, with an impressive 96% of students showing strong motivation to learn English. This high level of motivation suggests a robust educational environment that values and supports English language learning. A notable 95% of the students are familiar with Zoom, indicating that the majority have access to and are likely using advanced digital learning platforms. This high familiarity reflects a progressive approach to integrating technology into the educational experience, likely facilitated by both the school administration and the students' home environments.

Furthermore, every student at SMAN 1 Kuala can browse Google and has a social media account, underscoring a comprehensive level of digital literacy and engagement. These skills are essential for modern learning, allowing students to efficiently gather information and communicate effectively.

On the other hand, SMAN 1 Tadu Raya had a smaller sample size, with only 12 students surveyed. Despite the limited number, 90% of the students reported a strong motivation to learn English, indicating a positive attitude towards English education within this small group. However, there is a significant gap in technological familiarity; only 30% of the students know about Zoom, while 70% have never accessed or heard of it. This lack of familiarity suggests potential challenges in accessing or utilizing online learning platforms, which could stem from limited resources or insufficient emphasis on digital literacy in the curriculum.

Most students at SMAN 1 Tadu Raya can browse Google, and 90% have social media accounts, indicating a basic level of digital proficiency. This proficiency is crucial for accessing educational content and engaging in digital communication, though it also highlights a discrepancy in familiarity with more specialized tools like Zoom.

Lastly, SMAN 1 Darul Makmur surveyed 32 students, revealing that a significant 97% of them are motivated to succeed in learning English. This high level of motivation indicates a strong commitment to academic achievement and a recognition of the importance of English proficiency in their future careers and education.

Technological familiarity among these students is exceptionally high, with 96% of them knowing about Zoom. This suggests that the majority of students have access to and experience with advanced online learning platforms, reflecting a tech-savvy student body. The remaining 4%

who have never accessed Zoom may point to a minority with limited access to technology or insufficient exposure to digital learning tools, highlighting a small but important gap that needs addressing to ensure inclusive access to educational technology.

Most students at SMAN 1 Darul Makmur are proficient in browsing Google, indicating that they possess essential digital literacy skills necessary for research and information gathering. Additionally, every student has a social media account, which emphasizes their engagement with digital communication and networking platforms. This universal digital engagement suggests that students are well-prepared to utilize technology for both educational and personal development purposes.

Overall, the data indicates that while students in these schools are highly motivated to learn English, there is variability in their familiarity with technology, particularly with Zoom. However, the majority of students have social media accounts and can browse Google, suggesting a baseline level of digital literacy. The *Haba Inggreh* application is widely regarded as a valuable tool for enhancing English language skills across all surveyed schools.

Later, in fostering the answer to the second research question, a set of questionnaire was also distributed. The result is as elaborated in the following.

When it comes to the *Haba Inggreh* application, 70% of the students at SMAN 1 Beutong strongly agreed that it helps improve their speaking and listening skills. This strong endorsement suggests that students are open to using digital tools for language learning and see tangible benefits from such applications. Implicitly, this also indicates that with increased exposure and training, students could become more comfortable and adept with a broader range of educational technologies, potentially enhancing their overall learning experience. The results imply that while there is a high level of motivation and basic digital proficiency among students, there is a need for increased efforts to familiarize them with more specialized educational tools like Zoom. Addressing this gap could further enhance their learning outcomes and better prepare them for the demands of modern education and future careers.

In SMAN 1 Suka Makmue, The strong endorsement of the *Haba Inggreh* application by 95% of the students highlights their positive reception towards integrating technology into their learning process. This implies that students are not only willing but also enthusiastic about using digital tools to enhance their language skills. Implicitly, this acceptance and recognition of the app's benefits suggest that the educational environment at SMAN 1 Seunagan is conducive to leveraging technology for learning. The students' positive attitude towards digital learning tools may also indicate that they are receiving adequate support and encouragement from their teachers and the school administration.

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In SMAN 1 Kuala, the fact that 95% of the students strongly believe the *Haba Inggreh* application enhances their English skills suggests a high degree of acceptance and perceived benefit from digital learning tools. Implicitly, this also indicates that students are likely receiving adequate support and training in using such applications, enhancing their overall learning experience and outcomes. This is similar to what is found in SMAN 1 Tadu Raya.

The endorsement of the *Haba Inggreh* application by 75% of the students at SMAN Tadu Raya, who strongly agree it helps improve their English speaking and listening skills, suggests a positive reception towards digital tools for language learning. Implicitly, this acceptance indicates a willingness among students to embrace technology for educational purposes, though it also points to a need for increased support and resources to bridge the technological gap.

Remarkably, 99% of the students strongly believe that the *Haba Inggreh* app is beneficial for improving their English speaking and listening skills at SMAN 1 Darul Makmur. This overwhelming endorsement implies that students have had positive experiences with the app and recognize its value in enhancing their language learning. Implicitly, this also suggests that the school's environment is supportive of integrating digital tools into the curriculum, providing students with the necessary resources and encouragement to utilize such applications effectively.

DISCUSSION

The data above indicates that while students in these schools are highly motivated to learn English, there is variability in their familiarity with technology, particularly with Zoom. However, the majority of students have social media accounts and can browse Google, suggesting a baseline level of digital literacy. The *Haba Inggreh* application is widely regarded as a valuable tool for enhancing English language skills across all surveyed schools. This widespread endorsement of the *Haba Inggreh* app emphasizes the potential for digital tools to significantly enhance language learning outcomes, provided that the necessary support and resources are available to address the existing technological gaps.

When comparing the findings from these six high schools to previous studies, several similarities and differences emerge. Past research has consistently highlighted the importance of motivation in language learning, which aligns with the high levels of motivation observed in this study. For example, Gardner's socio-educational model of language acquisition emphasizes the role of motivation as a key predictor of successful language learning outcomes. The high motivation levels reported in all surveyed schools reinforce this notion and suggest a strong foundation for effective English language education.

Moreover, the widespread use of social media among students across all school echoes findings from other studies that have noted the integral role of social media in modern education. Social media platforms are not only tools for communication but also serve as resources for collaborative learning and access to educational content. This high engagement with social media indicates that students are already comfortable with certain aspects of digital technology, which can be enhanced to introduce more advanced educational tools.

However, there are notable differences, particularly in terms of technological familiarity. Previous studies have shown that access to and familiarity with digital learning platforms like Zoom can significantly enhance educational outcomes. In this study, the variability in Zoom familiarity across different schools highlights a crucial gap. For instance, schools like SMAN 1 Seunagan and SMAN 1 Darul Makmur, where a high percentage of students are familiar with Zoom, contrast sharply with SMAN 1 Beutong and SMAN 1 Tadu Raya, where a significant portion of students lack this familiarity.

This discrepancy may be attributed to several factors, including differences in school resources, the digital infrastructure available to students, and the emphasis placed on digital literacy within the curriculum. Schools with higher familiarity levels likely have better access to technological resources and more robust support systems for integrating technology into the classroom. Conversely, schools with lower familiarity levels might be facing challenges such as limited access to devices, insufficient internet connectivity, or a lack of training for both students and teachers.

The positive reception of the *Haba Inggreh* application across all schools is a significant finding. This endorsement suggests that digital tools tailored to language learning can be highly effective, provided they are accessible and user-friendly. The app's success in enhancing speaking and listening skills points to its potential as a valuable resource in language education. This finding is consistent with other research that has demonstrated the benefits of educational technology in language acquisition, such as increased engagement, personalized learning experiences, and the ability to practice language skills in interactive environments.

However, the study also emphasizes the need for targeted interventions to bridge technological gaps. For example, providing training sessions for both students and teachers on how to effectively use digital tools like Zoom could enhance their overall digital literacy and improve learning outcomes. Additionally, investing in infrastructure to ensure that all students have access to necessary devices and reliable internet connectivity is crucial.

Another implicit insight from the study is the potential role of school administration and policy in shaping students'

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technological familiarity and motivation. Schools like SMAN 1 Seunagan and SMAN 1 Darul Makmur, where students show high technological familiarity and strong endorsement of digital learning tools, likely benefit from supportive policies and proactive administration efforts to integrate technology into the curriculum. This suggests that school leadership plays a critical role in fostering an environment conducive to digital learning.

Moreover, the study highlights the importance of addressing the digital divide, particularly in rural or under-resourced schools. Ensuring equitable access to digital tools and resources is essential for providing all students with the opportunity to benefit from modern educational technologies. Policymakers and educators must work together to identify and address barriers to technology access, such as cost, availability, and training.

In short, the research questionnaire conducted across six high schools provides valuable insights into students' motivation, technological familiarity, and their perception of the *Haba Inggreh* application. The high levels of motivation observed across all schools are encouraging and suggest a strong foundation for effective English language education. However, the variability in technological familiarity, particularly with Zoom, highlights significant gaps that need to be addressed to ensure that all students can fully benefit from digital learning tools.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the research questionnaire conducted across six high schools provides a comprehensive look into students' motivation to learn English, their familiarity with technology, and their perception of the *Haba Inggreh* application. The high levels of motivation found across all schools highlight a strong foundation for effective English language education. However, the varying levels of technological familiarity, especially with tools like Zoom, reveal significant gaps that must be addressed to ensure all students can fully benefit from digital learning resources. The widespread positive reception of the *Haba Inggreh* app underscores the potential of well-designed educational technology to enhance language learning.

One major limitation of this study is the sample size and its geographic focus. The survey was conducted in only six high schools, which may not fully represent the broader student population. Additionally, the technological resources available to these schools might not be reflective of other regions, especially those with different socio-economic conditions. Future research should consider a larger and more diverse sample to provide a more comprehensive understanding of these issues.

The implications of this study are clear: while motivation among students is high, there is a pressing need to improve access to and familiarity with digital learning tools. Schools must invest in infrastructure and training to bridge the

technological gap. Teachers and students alike need ongoing support to effectively integrate these tools into their learning and teaching processes. Policymakers should prioritize funding and resources to ensure equitable access to technology across all schools.

For future research, it would be beneficial to explore the specific barriers that prevent students from accessing and using digital tools like Zoom. Understanding these obstacles can help in designing targeted interventions. Additionally, examining the long-term impact of using applications like *Haba Inggreh* on students' language proficiency would provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of such tools over time. Research could also explore the role of teacher training and support in enhancing the integration of technology in classrooms.

In summary, while the study reveals a high motivation for learning English among students, it also highlights significant technological gaps. Addressing these gaps through improved access, training, and support will be crucial in leveraging digital tools to enhance language learning. Future research should aim to broaden the scope and delve deeper into the specific challenges and long-term impacts of digital learning tools in education.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is funded by the grant of Directorate General of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in 2024 number 108/UN59/LPPM-PL/2024.

DISCLOSURE

The authors report no conflicts of interest in this work.

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